

LSST DESC Science Overview

Change Record¹

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¹Most of the text in this document has its origin in the first sections of the LSST DESC Science Roadmap. The last version, v2.6, including its change record, can be accessed on [zenodo](#). For ease of maintainability, the Science Roadmap was split into a Science Overview Document and a separate Science Plan.

LSST DESC Science Overview

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1 Executive Summary

The Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC) was established in 2012 to develop and execute a high-level plan for the study of dark energy and associated fundamental physics of the Universe with LSST data. The Rubin Observatory Project will create “prompt” (nightly alerts) and “data release” (annual catalog) data products, but will not perform science analyses with those datasets. DESC is focused on undertaking a precise and timely analysis of the Rubin Observatory data release products to optimally extract dark sector science, including dark energy, tests of the properties of gravity on cosmological scales, and dark matter.

LSST data will constrain both the cosmic expansion history and the growth in the amplitude of density fluctuations as functions of redshift. This will allow us to constrain key dark sector parameters, including the equation-of-state parameter of dark energy, the growth rate of the amplitude of matter inhomogeneities as a function of redshift, and the level of anisotropies of large-scale structures as measured across the sky. We will also carry out important consistency tests of the properties of gravity. In addition, we will provide constraints on the mean curvature of the Universe and the sum of neutrino masses. Our science goals require an exquisite understanding of possible systematic errors and therefore detailed studies of the impact of instrumental, atmospheric, Galactic, and extragalactic processes on LSST data. From this, we will establish accurate estimates of uncertainties to enable new insights into the physics of the dark Universe.

DESC is organized around working groups that focus on analysis, computing and simulation, and technical tasks. We describe in this document each working group and its research priorities to provide an overview of the major research and development areas covered by DESC. Cross-working group activities are essential to the success of DESC and are supported by our collaborative and inclusive approach to our common goals. This approach supports the development and comparison of multiple, alternative algorithms to find optimal solutions to technical problems and include them in the analysis pipelines.

DESC is committed to integrating and maintaining equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) at the core of its values, and to providing a positive, empowering environment for all of its members. DESC has also developed and adopted a **Code of Conduct** and a set of related practices that emphasize the Collaboration’s commitment to collegial and respectful behavior by members in every aspect of collaboration life. This is essential to ensuring that all members, from junior to senior, from all nations and backgrounds, feel able and encouraged to fully contribute to the Collaboration without fear of harassment, marginalization, or exclusion.

2 Introduction

Vera C. Rubin Observatory has been designed to conduct a deep survey of the Southern sky, the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), with the fast, wide-field optical Simonyi Survey Telescope. The experiment is organized with the Rubin facility (the Telescope, Camera, and Data Management system) separate from the Rubin science community. While Rubin Observatory is responsible for generating and processing the petabyte-scale imaging data to create science-ready catalogs (as well as designing and executing the survey itself), the broader scientific community will execute the scientific analysis of these catalogs. The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC) is the largest of several currently active science collaborations within this community, focused principally on the use of LSST to study observable signatures of “dark sector” physics, including dark energy, dark matter, neutrinos, and signatures of inflation. The goals of DESC are aligned with the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) High Energy Physics (HEP) science priorities outlined in the 2014 [Report of the Particle Physics Project Prioritization Panel \(P5\)](#) and in the [European Astroparticle Physics Strategy 2017-2026](#).

The volume and complexity of LSST data will be orders of magnitude greater than for data from precursor surveys and brings the potential for order-of-magnitude improvements in our understanding of dark sector physics. Improving our understanding of the physics of dark energy and dark matter is one of the primary science objectives for the Rubin experiment and the central focus of DESC.

2.1 The Goals of the Dark Energy Science Collaboration

2.1.1 Sensitivity to a Broad Set of Cosmological Parameters

The principal science goals of DESC are to use Rubin data to study observable signatures of dark sector physics, including dark energy, tests of the properties of gravity on cosmological scales, and dark matter. LSST data will constrain both the cosmic expansion history (which is related to the density and curvature of space) and the growth in the amplitude of density fluctuations as a function of redshift. Examples of key dark sector parameters that DESC will constrain include:

- the equation-of-state parameter of dark energy (measured as a function of redshift), including tests for deviation from a cosmological constant model and evolution in time;
- the growth rate of the amplitude of matter inhomogeneities as a function of redshift, to determine whether it is consistent with that predicted given the expansion history (i.e., Hubble “drag”) or whether it deviates from that, as may occur for gravitational models

that deviate from General Relativity (“modified gravity” theories). This includes tests for gravitational “screening” effects in dense environments, as are predicted in some modified gravity models;

- consistency tests of the properties of gravity as inferred from the propagation of light in comparison to the properties inferred from the motions and distribution of massive matter, as another test of potential signatures of modified gravity models; and
- the level of anisotropy of large-scale structure as measured across the sky, a phenomenon predicted by some dark energy models.

DESC will also provide astrophysical constraints on complementary cosmological parameters including:

- the sum of the neutrino masses; in combination with constraints on mass differences from neutrino oscillation experiments, this can determine whether the neutrino hierarchy is “normal” or “inverted”; and
- the mean curvature of the Universe, testing whether the overall geometry of the Universe is indeed Euclidean.
- the production mechanism, mass range, and non-gravitational interactions of dark matter particles (e.g., self-interaction cross section, decay lifetime), as well as limits on the abundance of massive compact objects such as primordial black holes.

The constraints on these parameters from LSST will complement those from the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI), and so DESC will help meet the P5 goals related to understanding the properties of neutrinos and the physics behind primordial inflation. In addition, their consideration is also vital to disentangle degeneracies between these phenomena and the dark energy effects described above.

2.1.2 Accurate Characterization and Mitigation of a Wide Range of Potential Systematic Effects

DESC is working to characterize and quantify the impact of an array of instrumental, atmospheric, and astrophysical systematic effects. These must be understood to a far deeper level than for current surveys so that their effects can be mitigated down to the LSST noise floor. For example, systematic astrophysical effects such as intrinsic alignments (IAs) of galaxy orientations, the cluster mass-observable relation, and the connection between Type Ia supernova luminosities and their host galaxy properties can both degrade and bias cosmological parameter inferences if not explicitly accounted for.

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Meeting the full potential of LSST for DESC science objectives will require understanding how the performance of Rubin Observatory, including LSST Science Pipelines, couples to our ability to constrain cosmological parameters. Simulating and modeling both the Universe and LSST (from the underlying cosmology to the performance of the telescope and camera to physical effects associated with its sensors) will be integral to our understanding of the capabilities of the LSST for characterizing cosmology. The scale and complexity of the preparations ahead are substantial and will require:

- characterization of the impact of instrumental, atmospheric, Galactic, and extragalactic systematic contaminants to the level necessary to achieve the collaboration’s dark sector science goals, as encapsulated in the DESC Science Requirements Document (SRD; [The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al. 2018](#));
- establishment of quantitative budgets for errors due to, e.g., instrumental systematic effects that may be imperfectly removed in software, leading to a need to reprocess a subset of the LSST data with varying choices for how the systematic bias mitigation is done; this may also necessitate non-negligible work on algorithmic development beyond that initially planned by Rubin Data Management, enabling DESC to investigate potential algorithms and share what we learn with the Rubin Project to improve the quality of the data products in a way that benefits cosmological and other science cases, and ensure that the final data ultimately meet requirements on systematic uncertainties for cosmological probes;
- continued construction and validation of DESC simulations of the LSST data set, (re-)processing, and analysis pipelines that will perform world-class cosmological analyses with the LSST data using the five main probes of dark energy (weak lensing, galaxy clustering, clusters of galaxies, type Ia supernovae, and strong lensing);
- analysis and reprocessing of precursor survey datasets, e.g. [DES](#), [HSC-SSP](#), and [KiDS](#), and incorporation of lessons learned from precursor surveys;
- determination of quantitative requirements on, and use of ancillary data from, other facilities (e.g., spectroscopy, multi-wavelength data and complementary, concurrent photometric survey data), as highlighted in a 2015 NRC report on [Optimizing the U.S. Ground-Based Optical and Infrared Astronomy System \(Elmegreen et al. 2015\)](#);
- development of the capabilities and coordination of the DESC team, including training of the next generation of DESC researchers and leaders.

Prioritization of these activities will be driven by our understanding of the key limiting systematic uncertainties that must be reduced/mitigated in order to achieve our scientific goals.

With the DESC SRD ([The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al. 2018](#)), we have started to place requirements on our level of control of systematic biases for elements of the analysis that are under our influence (beyond those already described by the Rubin Observatory Project’s Science Requirement Document [LPM-17](#)). We will continue to refine the SRD and fill in missing pieces to establish a full picture of our requirements. How close we are to meeting those requirements will inform how work is prioritized in DESC, and/or how it is carried out.

2.2 Structure of the Dark Energy Science Collaboration

LSST DESC was established in June 2012 and the collaboration has grown steadily since then, with more than 1100 members from more than 15 countries (including 241 voting Full Members and 45 Builders) as of February 2023. Scientific activities in DESC are structured and overseen through its [Governance Plan](#). Work is distributed across seventeen working groups organized under Analysis, Computing & Simulation, and Technical Coordinator Teams, who in turn report to the Spokesperson.

DESC is committed to integrating and maintaining equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) at the core of its values, and to providing a positive, empowering environment for all of its members. The collaborative, inclusive, project-driven approach in DESC to achieving our common goals is described in the [Publication Policy](#) and the [Software Policy](#). The collaborative approach also supports the development and comparison of multiple, alternative algorithms and solutions to technical problems and their inclusion in the analysis pipelines. Having appropriate structures in place is essential to facilitate and motivate collaborative coordination. Collaboration structures are designed to facilitate and motivate collaborative coordination of DESC activities, and give appropriate recognition for sustained and critical efforts in preparing for the LSST data analysis.

DESC strives to provide career development opportunities for early-career members as they transition through PhD, postdoc, and junior faculty positions, to become leaders in cosmology. DESC ensures visibility of junior members through speaking opportunities (the DESC Speakers Bureau plays a critical role here) and recognition of effort reflected in publications, senior member mentoring and support, through letters of reference, and paths to leadership roles in science and governance activities. The DESC [Builder Status Policy](#) provides another mechanism for recognizing those who have carried out extensive efforts in the collaboration.

DESC has developed and adopted a [Code of Conduct](#) and a set of related practices that emphasize the collaboration’s commitment to collegial and respectful behavior between members in every aspect of collaboration life. The intent is to ensure that all members, from junior to senior, from all nations and backgrounds, feel able and encouraged to fully contribute to the

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Collaboration without fear of harassment, marginalization, or exclusion.

2.3 Timelines

A crucial milestone for DESC will be the delivery of cosmology results based on the first year of LSST data (i.e., the data products that comprise LSST Data Release 2, DR2). With this milestone in mind, we present here the timeline and schedule of DESC activities until October 2026. [Figure 2.3.1](#) provides an overview of the DESC schedule from the start of the first Data Challenge (DC1, [Sánchez et al. 2020](#)) in 2015/16 to the release of DR2 in 2026 in the upper half of the image.

We show two simulated Data Challenges (DC1 and DC2, [LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration \(LSST DESC\) et al. 2021](#)) to support the creation and validation of the data analysis and simulation pipelines. This pair of Data Challenges of increasing scope and complexity plays a central role in the collaboration’s effort to prepare for the first year of LSST data. The DCs are collaboration-centered activities that use tailored simulated datasets to test and validate the tools and software infrastructure that will be used to analyze LSST data. DC1 was limited in scope and the simulation was largely focused on two individual working groups’

Figure 2.3.1: Schedule of DESC activities through US Fiscal Year 2026 as of January 2023, based on the re-baseline of the Rubin schedule. We show in gray the DESC schedule with two simulated Data Challenges (DC1 and DC2) as well as Science Readiness and Early Science phases. In the lower half of the figure we show the Rubin schedule: the blue shaded boxes indicate the currently scheduled period for LSSTCam integration, testing, and on-sky observations as well as the LSST Science Operations start. The red shaded boxes in the bottom row show the target release dates for Data Previews based on simulated data (DP0.1 and DP0.2) and on LSSTCam data commissioning data (DP1, DP2), and the first Data Release (DR1) after the start of LSST Operations. For the release dates, we show the most optimistic dates provided by Rubin (January 2023). [Table 2.3.1](#) also shows the estimated uncertainties on these dates (~ 5 months). All data release dates are currently uncertain and should be treated as approximate.

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Date	Description
2021-06-30	Deliver DP0.1
2022-06-30	Complete Delivery of DP0.2
July 2024 - August 2024	System First Light
September 2024 - October 2024	Complete Delivery of DP1
November 2024 - February 2025	LSST Survey Start
May 2025 - August 2025	Complete Delivery of DP2
November 2025 - April 2026	Complete Delivery of DR1

Table 2.3.1: Rubin Operations Top Milestones as of January 2023. The left column includes delivery and starting dates. For future milestones, date ranges are provided. [Figure 2.3.1](#) reports the earliest possible dates if a range is given.

needs. DC2 features increased sophistication and more cross-working group analyses, with a coordinated collaboration-wide approach to simulation design, production, and validation, followed by analysis within working groups. The DC2 simulated data were publicly released and are the input to Rubin’s first Data Previews, DP0.1 and DP0.2. These first Data Previews offer an opportunity for DESC members and the Rubin science community to explore the Rubin Science Platform (RSP). DESC analysis of the DC2 simulated data set is still ongoing in 2023.

The time period following DC2 generation includes the next steps to achieving science readiness – the analysis of both simulated datasets and precursor data. The final phase of DESC preparation begins with the release of on-sky data from LSSTCam data (Data Preview 1, Data Preview 2), until the release of the first full year of processed LSST data (LSST Data Release 2). This era is marked as “Early Science” with the understanding that early data from LSSTCam are suitable for opportunistic and creative projects with the aim to start demonstrating the science potential of on-sky data. During the Early Science era, all DESC members will for the first time have access to Rubin data. DESC is providing inputs into the design of commissioning on-sky observing strategy in response to solicitations from the Project, and will eventually make use of data from the Rubin Observatory full science Camera (LSSTCam) to test DESC analysis pipelines and their interfaces to Rubin Observatory/LSST Data Management (DM) products. During the Early Science period, our priority is to validate DESC pipelines and have them working at appropriate scale to take full advantage of DP1 and DP2, and the first six months of survey data, captured by DR1.

For context, the lower panel of [Figure 2.3.1](#) shows the planned schedule of data delivery milestones from the Rubin Observatory Project, including a series of the planned Data Pre-

views (DPs) prior to the first LSST Data Release (DR1) based on the first 6 months of survey operations. Some DESC members will have the opportunity to directly participate in the Rubin commissioning based on their successful responses in 2021 to Rubin’s Announcement of Opportunity via [SITCOMTN-010](#). [Table 2.3.1](#) summarizes the Rubin’s Operations top milestones including estimated date ranges.

2.4 Useful Resources

For more details about LSST DESC and recent progress, we provide a list of publicly available documents and resources below. In general, all DESC public documents can be found on the [LSST DESC webpage](#). We highlight some of them here for convenience.

- [DESC Planning documents](#) – a set of DESC documents (SRM, SRD, and Data Management Plan) and relevant Rubin Observatory Project Documents.
- [DESC Policies](#) – the DESC Governance Plan, the Code of Conduct, and six DESC policies.
- [DESC Publications](#) – a current list (updated daily) of all DESC publications.
- [DESC Projects](#) – a current list (updated regularly) of all DESC Projects, ongoing, paused, and completed.

3 Working Groups

DESC is a very large collaboration with many projects and collaborative activities. In order to provide an organizational structure that helps DESC members to navigate the many ongoing activities, working groups have been established and are organized into Analysis, Computing & Simulation, and Technical areas overseen by corresponding DESC Coordinator Teams. In this section, we provide a brief summary of the key research priorities of each working group. Cross-working group activities are also important in DESC, as is leveraging the knowledge and expertise of individuals associated with the Rubin Observatory Project.

DESC targets five main probes of dark energy enabled by the LSST data:

1. Weak gravitational lensing (WL) – the deflection of light from distant sources due to the bending of space-time by baryonic and dark matter along the line of sight, which allows measurement of the growth rate of cosmic structure (and therefore is also sensitive to dark energy).
2. Large-scale structure (LSS) – the large-scale power spectrum for the spatial distribution of matter as a function of redshift. This includes the Baryonic Acoustic Oscillations (BAO) measurement of the distance-redshift relation.
3. Type Ia supernovae (SN) – luminosity distance as a function of redshift measured with Type Ia SN as standardizable candles.
4. Galaxy clusters (CL) – the spatial density, distribution, and masses of galaxy clusters as a function of redshift.
5. Strong gravitational lensing (SL) – the angular displacement, morphological distortion, and time delay for the multiple images of a source object due to a massive foreground object.

Both weak and strong lensing can also probe the evolution of cosmic geometry. This list includes the four techniques (WL, LSS, SN, CL) described in the 2006 Report of the Dark Energy Task Force (DETF). The goal of DESC is not just to carry out these analyses in isolation, but also to combine them. DESC working groups encapsulate high-priority activities that enable, relate to, or combine results from the dark energy probes.

3.1 Computing & Simulation Working Groups

3.1.1 Computing

Summary: The Computing (CO) group must provide several capabilities to DESC: effective usage of the available computing resources, tools to run and manage large productions, a software environment for collaboration and external code to function in, data access tools, including creation and maintenance of databases, promotion of standard data formats, and other common tools needed by the various WGs. DESC must also have a distributed code development environment to allow the geographically dispersed DESC membership to work together on a common DESC code base. The overarching vision for the DESC computing environment is that members should find it easy to access the Rubin project’s software tools and data, develop analysis code that can use modules written by others within the collaboration, incorporate third-party code (such as the HEALPix library), and track and share results. This will enable the collaboration to identify the optimal algorithms, modules, and pipelines for different problems.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Investigation (or coordination of investigations) on how to make the best use of available and upcoming facilities, such as Perlmutter at NERSC.
2. Investigation of possible database solutions, either for DESC-wide use or specific to a particular WG or subset of WGs
3. Investigation and/or development of tools for data management and tracking.
4. Development of a DESC software environment for developers and production processing.

3.1.2 Cosmological and Survey Simulations

Summary: The Cosmological and Survey Simulations (CSS) group merges two formerly separate working groups, Cosmological Simulations and Survey Simulations.

Cosmological simulations and the mock catalogs derived from these simulations have enabled the data challenges as well as a broad range of activities, including the testing and development of the analysis pipelines described in this document. Simulated datasets are needed in a number of forms, including halo catalogs from gravity-only simulations, simulated observational catalogs, and inputs to image simulations. For each of these datasets, there are a variety of levels of required fidelity in order to meet the intended scientific goals for their use. Thus,

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the validation of the simulated datasets against both observational data and theoretical predictions is an important and integral component of the effort. The improvement in fidelity, which, in general, involves optimizing a complex set of requirements can only be achieved in close coordination with other working groups and a detailed understanding of the interfaces, requirements, and available resources. Another key component of the effort is the generation of fast prediction tools to enable the development of inference pipelines for cosmological analyses.

The CSS group will also coordinate the development and application of DESC software for simulating Rubin-like images, e.g., using the imSim software package taking as input the galaxy catalogs produced by the cosmological simulations. As Rubin operations approach, CSS will support the application of image simulations for validating survey performance during commissioning and the science verification phase, and ultimately, during operations.

Priorities:

Our priorities for the CSS group are presented here separately for cosmological simulations and image/catalog simulations.

Cosmological simulation priorities:

1. Galaxy-Halo Connection

At present, the only feasible method for constructing large-scale galaxy catalogs involves modeling the galaxy-halo connection to populate dark-matter halos with galaxies. These models necessarily contain a variety of approximations. The level of detail and the demands on the fidelity of the models will increase commensurately with the sophistication of the cosmological analyses that are being pursued. The CSS group, in collaboration with the analysis working groups, must develop a series of staged improvements to the existing galaxy-halo connection models.

2. Validation

The level of fidelity of simulated catalogs to the real Universe is assessed by validation testing. The translation of the evolving science activities of the analysis working groups into tests that can be applied to simulated catalogs is ongoing collaborative work with the CSS group. An understanding of the tests that can be applied, the available and relevant data for the test, and the interpretation of the test results are all critical for determining the limitations of the catalogs. The test results also serve as a guide for prioritizing improvements to the simulations: the most significant deviations between reality and simulations point to areas requiring more development.

3. Hydrodynamical simulations and characterization of baryon effects

3: Working Groups - Cosmological and Survey Simulations

High-fidelity simulations including gas physics and sub-grid models pose a tremendous challenge for the cosmological simulations group. Nevertheless, they will play a very important role for understanding systematic effects, particularly for cluster and weak lensing studies. Over the next few years, both the scale and fidelity of these simulations need to be improved. In parallel with this work, complementary efforts to develop alternative methods for including baryonic effects and to develop strategies for mitigating baryonic effects must also be continued.

4. Development of prediction tools

The development of fast and accurate prediction tools for quantities of cosmological interest such as mass functions, power spectra, concentration-mass relations, etc., for many different cosmologies will be a critical capability for upcoming analyses. These will be used in inference pipelines for extracting cosmological information from the simulated data sets and later from observational data.

5. Covariance estimation

The accurate estimation of covariances, which will be crucial for future cosmological analyses, is an outstanding problem that needs to be solved. Brute-force methods are not currently feasible, but will become more viable in the future. In the meantime, it is important to continue to develop approximate methods and to understand better the number and scale of the simulations required to obtain sufficiently accurate estimates for cosmological inference.

Survey simulation priorities:

1. Improving the fidelity and usability of the image simulation tools.

- (a) Implement ray tracing of light through the telescope so that we can adequately model vignetting, stray light, diffraction, ghost images, etc.
- (b) Use GPUs to speed up modeling of charge redistribution in the sensors owing to electrostatic effects.
- (c) Refactor how sky images are rendered so that electrostatic effects in the sensors can be more realistically modeled for overlapping and blended sources.
- (d) Use the GalSim config framework to enable interoperability with other GalSim-based packages, e.g., for joint Roman-Rubin simulations, as well as to enable special purpose simulations needed to support development efforts such as the shear measurement pipeline.

- (e) Improve the interfaces to the extragalactic catalogs and other inputs to the image simulations such as Milky Way stars, supernovae, AGNs, and other time-varying objects.
- 2. Support synthetic source injection efforts for both real and simulated data in collaboration with the Rubin DM team.
- 3. Investigate catalog emulation, using image simulations as training data, in order to have a more efficient option for studying cosmological parameter space than full end-to-end image simulation and image processing exercises.

3.1.3 Science Release and Validation

Summary: The Science Release and Validation (SRV) working group is responsible for ensuring that Rubin data is high-enough quality for the analyses in DESC, and contributing new value-added information for these. The Rubin data sets include Data Previews and Data Releases. The SRV WG will serve as the point of contact for the Collaboration for discussing any aspects related to the data sets provided by Rubin, in order to find support or common issues.

Priorities: The priorities can be broadly characterized as follows:

- 1. Building a testing infrastructure that will test data previews and data releases before ingesting the data into the analysis pipelines.
- 2. Connecting all higher-level validation efforts throughout DESC, either keeping track of them or providing support.
- 3. Constructing value-added data products, such as new flags, classifiers, and photometric estimates, to complement data sets provided by Rubin.
- 4. Serving as a hub for scientists in DESC to cooperate and describe issues with any aspects related with data, to find solutions or share findings, and possibly provide feedback to the Rubin Observatory Data Management team.

The SRV WG will work with the Computing WG on the design and implementation of the infrastructure required to access, curate, and otherwise manage the data products used or created by the analysis pipelines.

3.2 Technical Working Groups and Task Force

3.2.1 Blending

Summary: Two or more objects are described as “blended” if their images overlap enough that each object’s properties cannot be accurately measured independently. The current LSST DM science pipeline addresses the challenges presented by blended objects in three steps: (i) object *detection*, which includes identification of above-threshold regions and approximate positions of objects within them; (ii) construction of individual object images or models in which a portion of the flux in each pixel is assigned to each blended object (*deblender*); and (iii) measurement of position, shape, flux, etc., for the deblended objects. Detection, deblending and measurement can in principle be an iterative process, and combinations of these operations, such as deblending and measurement, could be done simultaneously.

The original LSST DM deblender, which is derived from the single-band SDSS deblender and has been used in all Hyper Suprime-Cam releases to date, is known to be inadequate for LSST depths. A new multi-band deblender `scarlet` has been integrated in LSST DM. While the SDSS deblender is still used for calexp images, coadded images are now being deblended using `scarlet lite`, a version of `scarlet` optimized for handling Rubin images. Given the challenges in dealing with blended objects, LSST DM has communicated that it welcomes research, development, and testing of new and existing algorithms.

Goals of the Blending (BL) WG include establishing quantitative metrics for the impacts of blending and measuring the baseline performance of existing algorithms and those under development, to compare to established requirements (e.g., on shear biases). In addition, missing requirements will be established (e.g., impacts of blending on photometric redshifts). An additional goal of the WG is to explore and test new algorithms for detection, deblending, and/or measurement of blended objects, including machine-learning approaches.

Some studies of performance metrics involve working with pixel-level simulations or data. For detection algorithms, performance metrics could describe whether blended objects are accurately recognized as blends, unrecognized as blends, iteratively recognized as blends, shredded into multiple objects, etc. The metrics for deblending and measurement algorithms will include the accuracy of shape measurements and photometry for blended objects. Impacts of detection failures on higher-level quantities, such as photo- z estimates or 2-point correlation functions, can be studied with pixel-level datasets, or with catalog-level simulations (with no pixel simulation) if accurate surrogates for detection and deblending performance can be identified based on only catalog-level quantities.

In support of these goals, BL WG activities include design and implementation of tools for training and testing algorithms (e.g., the `BlendingToolKit`), and the coordination and

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curation of real data sets (ground and space) and simulations. The BL WG hosts DESC efforts to support the development of synthetic source injection (SSI), in which images of real or simulated objects are injected into raw science data – either real or simulated. These data are then processed through to final imaging and catalogue outputs. Since SSI provides information on sources where the “truth” is known, analysis of these data allows us to assess the accuracy of output source catalogs, including for blended sources, as well as the fidelity of associated data processing steps such as sky subtraction.

As a cross-cutting WG, the BL WG provides a communication channel and a forum for sharing relevant expertise across the many WGs affected by blending challenges, and between DESC and LSST DM. Many of the research priorities described below involve more than one DESC WG and are coordinated within the BL WG. A few activities are focused within a particular WG (e.g., CL) but benefit from feedback from the broader community engaged in the BL WG. In addition to regular meetings, the BL WG engages in organizing workshops that involve experts in LSST DM and members of other LSST science collaborations who have relevant expertise in areas impacted by blending.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Develop blending requirements for dark energy science. Connect detection, shear calibration, and photometric redshift requirements to requirements on residual blending effects, including detection and deblending errors, to feed into the DESC Science Requirements Document.
2. Evaluate techniques being developed to measure the impacts of blending on object detection, shear estimation, and photometric redshift measurements, including Metadetection algorithms and simulation-based forward modeling.
3. Explore new algorithms for detection, deblending, and/or measurement of blended objects. Investigate whether color information can be used to identify blends and correct the measured shear and photometric redshifts. Explore machine-learning (ML) approaches that leverage recent advances in “deep learning,” Gaussian processes, or other methods. For example, deep morphology priors are being incorporated in the `scarlet` framework. While ML approaches to deblending may not be mature enough to be included in LSST DM pipelines for initial processing, these approaches may have a significant role to play in detection and deblending later in Rubin operations.
4. Study the impacts of residual blending effects on dark energy science in coordination with analysis WGs, including, but not limited to, CL, LSS, PZ, WL.
5. Explore the effectiveness of joint pixel-level processing of deep LSST images and high

spatial resolution space-based images for mitigating blending-related systematic effects on shear estimation and redshift measurements – for example, using deep LSST coadds with forced deblending based on a catalog derived from space-based observations, or joint pixel processing of LSST and Euclid / Roman data. Note that DESC does not have the resources to carry out a full joint pixel-level processing; however, smaller-scale processing to inform a full processing with additional resources, and studies to understand the benefits of forced deblending versus joint pixel-level processing, would be valuable and in scope for the BL WG.

3.2.2 Photometric Corrections

Summary: Photometric calibration uncertainties have a major impact on the measurement of the Dark Energy equation of state with SNe Ia, as well as other dark energy probes, via their impact on photometric redshifts. DESC-specific calibration requirements, essentially driven by SN Ia cosmology, are especially stringent and may be summarized with two key quantities: the *relative* (band-to-band) flux calibration needs to be controlled at the 0.1% level, and the mean wavelength of the survey passbands should be known with an accuracy of 0.1-nm according to the DESC Science Requirements Document v1 ([The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al. 2018](#)) and to the study performed by [Hazenberget al. \(2018\)](#).

The Photometric Corrections Working Group (PCWG) works alongside the Rubin Project to ensure that these requirements will be met. The production of calibrated magnitudes involves algorithms and procedures implemented in Level 1 and Level 2 pipelines and is ultimately under the responsibility of LSST DM. PCWG work focuses on (1) the characterization of the Primary flux standards used to set the survey flux scale (2) the validation of LSST DM algorithms, notably point source photometry and survey uniformity (3) in-situ filter metrology using the Collimated Beam Projector (CoBP) (4) the measurement of the atmospheric transmission from the Auxiliary telescope. All these aspects require a close connection with the Rubin Project. Other aspects of photometric calibration are more specific to DESC – e.g., the mitigation of the effects of Galactic extinction on calibrated magnitudes. Within DESC, PCWG works with the Science Working Groups to evaluate how the expected photometric calibration uncertainties impact dark energy probes.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group — in no particular order — can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. *Primary flux scale:* As of today, the primary flux references are defined using models of white dwarf atmospheres. While there are hints that this is probably accurate at the 1% level, this needs to be checked to reach an accuracy of 0.1%. Several projects aim to

3: Working Groups - Photometric Corrections

directly compare the white dwarf flux scale and the detector-based flux scale maintained at NIST. Two of these projects are being carried out by members of PCWG. *starDICE* re-observes primary flux standards with a dedicated photometric telescope whose calibration is monitored in real time with a stable, NIST-calibrated light source, made of 24 narrow-spectrum LEDs. *SCALA* carries out a similar program, with the SNIFS instrument, mounted on the UH-2.2-m. The projects have reached precisions of $\sim 1\%$ (*SCALA*) and $\sim 2\text{-}3\%$ (*starDICE*) and are being upgraded to reach sub-percent accuracy. *starDICE* is also used as a test bench for filter metrology.

2. *Validate LSST DM point source photometry*: Point source photometry algorithms are the main link in the flux calibration chain. It is therefore essential to check that LSST DM flux measurements are not sensitive to observing conditions (seeing, background level) and are not affected by known biases (linearity, PSF chromaticity) at the per-mil level. This validation work may be carried out on precursor datasets, such as SNLS, DES, or HSC, or simulated data.
3. *Survey uniformity*: As with the validation of the point source photometry, quantifying and improving survey uniformity will require a combination of internal data checks and comparison to external datasets such as Gaia.
4. *Filter metrology*: To compare supernova or galaxy fluxes to model predictions (e.g., to deliver SN distances or galaxy photometric redshifts), one needs models of the survey passbands. Such models are assembled from testbench measurements of the optical components (mirrors, lenses and filters). To monitor the evolution of survey passbands as a function of time, the Rubin baseline plan is to use a CoBP, a monochromatic pencil beam to perform in situ measurements of the survey passbands. The accuracy of this method is being investigated. PCWG members are currently experimenting with a “precursor CoBP” to measure and then to monitor in situ the passbands of the *starDICE* telescopes – with plans to use this precursor CoBP on larger survey telescopes (Blanco, ZTF, Subaru).
5. *Atmospheric transmission monitoring & participation in the commissioning and operations of the Auxiliary telescope (AuxTel)*: The transmission of the atmosphere at the time of observation is part of the effective passband determination. The 1.2-m Rubin AuxTel is equipped with an instrument that can deliver either images or low-resolution slitless spectroscopy. Monitoring spectra of stars using AuxTel allows constraints on the (wavelength-dependent component) of the variations of the atmospheric transmission along the line of sight. PCWG is involved in the preparation of the AuxTel observing

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plan, and the development and validation of the AuxTel photometric and spectroscopic pipeline.

Enhancements: Some research topics that could lead to enhancements to the baseline Rubin analysis from this working group are as follows.

1. Obtaining a flux calibration and survey passband determination more accurate than the survey base plans. This would be an enhancement of the entire survey baseline.
2. SN cosmology would significantly benefit from a survey calibrated at the per-mil level, as the constraints on a varying dark energy equation of state will go from “marginal” to “stringent”.

3.2.3 Point-Spread Function

Summary: The LSST point-spread function (PSF) is a required element of most measurement algorithms, including those for astrometry, photometry, and shear estimation. As such, systematic errors in the PSF can potentially impact all DESC probes. The goals of this working group are to characterize and mitigate the impact of LSST PSF errors on LSST dark energy constraints.

Priorities: The priorities of the PSF working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Analysis of PSF systematic errors:
 - (a) Estimate the impact of specific PSF errors – for example, low-order PSF moment residuals, chromatic effects, and correlations thereof, on DESC dark energy constraints.
 - (b) Develop requirements on PSF residuals and correlation functions to limit the impact of PSF systematic errors.
 - (c) Develop mitigation strategies, such as techniques that can accurately marginalize over PSF systematic errors, or mitigations originating in survey strategy.
 - (d) Study how residual CCD systematic effects that are not strictly a convolution, but that can contaminate PSF models through their impact on the images of stars used for PSF estimation, impact dark energy constraints.
2. PSF modeling improvements:

- (a) In concert with Rubin Data Management’s plans for PSF estimation (see section 6.11.3, Full Visit PSF Estimation, of **LDM-151**) for Data Release data products (previously known as Level 2; see **LPM-231**), analyze new PSF modeling approaches – for example, a consistent physics-based model across the entire LSST focal plane – in the context of dark energy science.
- (b) Investigate the use of LSST wavefront sensor information to constrain the optical contribution to the PSF.
- (c) Explore methodology for modeling PSF chromaticity and including it in object measurement.

3. Increased understanding of PSF physics:

- (a) Review and exploit existing data, including specialized observations or laboratory measurements, to enhance our PSF modeling accuracy and/or help create higher fidelity PSF simulations.
- (b) Investigate connections between the observed PSF profiles and the physical conditions of the observations, including weather and other atmospheric effects, optical configurations, pointing direction (especially airmass), telescope flexure, and other time-dependent physical effects in the telescope or camera.

3.2.4 Sensor Anomalies

Summary: In the context of LSST, sensor anomalies refer to the departure of CCDs’ response from a perfectly Cartesian sampling of the image, with a linear response. These departures from perfection impact core measurements such as positions, fluxes and shapes. The Sensor Anomalies Working Group works in close connection with the Rubin Project and aims to characterize the LSST CCDs and develop methods to handle these anomalies, with a goal of minimizing their impact on dark energy measurements to within tolerances.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Dynamic distortions: These are the geometrical image distortions arising from charges accumulating during the image exposure due to electrostatic forces. The most striking manifestation of these distortions is the so-called “brighter-fatter effect.”
 - (a) Refine the relation between flat-field statistics and electrostatic quantities. Characterize how the covariance of flat-fields evolves with the signal level.

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- (b) Develop a detailed Poisson solver for deep-depleted CCDs that allows one to simulate drift trajectories, and study their alterations as charge accumulates.
 - (c) Use CCD data acquired on test benches to improve the use of flat-fields in the correction definition.
 - (d) Characterize the CCDs (and their demographics) with respect to the magnitude of the brighter-fatter effect and the related calibration products.
 - (e) Study whether real science images can provide direct input to a correction method, particularly because they contain strong charge gradients absent from flat fields.
 - (f) Provide improvements to the algorithms of the LSST Science Pipelines as knowledge improves.
2. Static non-uniformities: These are image distortions that are independent of the observed image, typically due to drift field inhomogeneity and spatial non-uniformities in the quantum efficiency of the sensor, which affect the flux measurements.
- (a) The spatial variations of impurity density are mostly visible as “tree rings”, which slowly modulate the effective size (and position) of pixels. A correction scheme depends on finely measuring those tree rings on flat-field images.
 - (b) The distortion due to weak fields at the sensor edges can be partially corrected using an effective drift field distortion model. Refining and testing these models will eventually extend the usable sensor area.
 - (c) The “tearing” feature is also a distortion of the drift field that can appear in some sensors. Tearing can be mitigated with hardware parameter optimisation, but there can be residual effects at the edges, between each sensor segment, which need to be taken into account.
 - (d) The “fringing” patterns appearing in flat fields at near-infrared wavelengths is caused by self-interference of the incoming light. The resulting spatial non-uniformities in the effective quantum efficiency vary rapidly with wavelength. Modelling these variations is key to accounting for this effect when observing in the red bands.
3. Sensor operation: These effects depend on the parameters used when operating the sensors – i.e. voltages, timings, and settings in the readout chain. While these effects can sometimes be mitigated by modifying operating parameters, metrics are needed to quantify whether the mitigation efforts are effective, and how much impact the residual effects would have on measurements.

3: Working Groups - Commissioning Task Force

- (a) The electronic chains are affected by nonlinearity, which should be corrected. Therefore, developing the nonlinearity measurement and analysis methodology for the ~ 3000 channels of the LSST Camera is essential; defining and measuring sensor full well is a related issue.
- (b) Crosstalk is a phenomenon that can impact science images. Due to its position dependence and potentially nonlinear nature, crosstalk must be carefully quantified.
- (c) The sensors are affected by charge transfer inefficiencies (CTI); the DESC accuracy requirements suggest revisiting the impact of CTI on position, shape and flux measurements.
- (d) The subtraction of the bias from the image is one step in instrument signature removal (ISR) that can be impacted by several effects arising at the level of the sensors and their readout: 2D structure of the bias, bias shifts, bias drifts, and other variations in time.

Enhancements: Some research topics that could lead to enhancements to the baseline LSST analysis for this working group are as follows.

1. Now that we have real image data with an LSST sensor on the Auxiliary Telescope, we can characterize the quality of our corrections, and possibly carry out specific engineering sky observations, ideally in coordination with the PSF WG.

3.2.5 Commissioning Task Force

Summary: The DESC Commissioning Task Force (CTF) is the interface between DESC and the Rubin Commissioning Team. The purpose of the CTF is to interact with and support the Commissioning Team, support DESC members who wish to work in the project commissioning effort directly, and design and carry out tests on the LSST commissioning data that will ensure DESC can make accurate fundamental physics measurements. The CTF has broad membership from across DESC, with engagement by members of Technical, Analysis, and Computing and Simulations working groups.

Prior to the start of the LSST survey, the Commissioning Team will commission the telescope, including the camera, and the associated software systems. The Commissioning Team will verify that the system is built to specifications and can achieve defined performance goals. A set of tests will be performed to demonstrate that each specification has indeed been met. DESC also has its own set of requirements on the performance of the Rubin system that are necessary to achieve the DESC science goals. In some cases, these requirements are more stringent than those specified in the Rubin construction plans; in other cases DESC requirements

3: Working Groups - Commissioning Task Force

are unique to DESC and are not currently envisioned to be tested by the Rubin Commissioning Team.

In June 2021, the Rubin Construction Project issued an Announcement of Opportunity for Community Engagement with Rubin Observatory Commissioning Effort ([SITCOMTN-010](#)), inviting “members of the US and Chilean LSST science communities to join the Rubin Commissioning Team in order to make value-added contributions that facilitate an efficient transition into LSST Operations”. The process culminated in the submission of Letters of Interest. The CTF shepherded this process for DESC members who wanted to contribute to the commissioning effort. Accepted groups participating in both the US/Chile Announcement of Opportunity Program and the Internal In-Kind Contribution Program (who are making contributions to Rubin Observatory Commissioning) began onboarding and work assignments in the second quarter of 2022.

As commissioning progresses up until the start of science operations, the CTF will act as the interface between DESC members working in the Commissioning Team, and the wider DESC community. The members will explain and share any publicly available findings from commissioning, and also act as a resource for the DESC teams working on the public Data Previews.

Priorities: The priorities of the Commissioning Task Force can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Updating lists already prepared by DESC of targets and fields ([Amon et al. 2020](#)) that could be observed during commissioning, based on the experience gained by the Commissioning Team. This includes highlighting to the Commissioning Team particular fields that will allow the DESC working groups to test their pipelines and analysis tools.
2. Iterating during commissioning with those taking on-sky observations on possible pointings/dithers, exposure sequences, external reference datasets, etc.
3. Identifying commissioning needs that are a high priority for DESC, would add value to the commissioning program, and be uniquely suited to commissioning data (as opposed to Data Previews).
4. Designing new tests for the Commissioning Team to undertake as well as utilizing DESC expertise to design and improve tests that are already envisioned.
5. Developing validation tests for assessing the quality and survey readiness of commissioning and early operations data.
6. Creating a comprehensive DESC commissioning plan.

7. Coordinating any future contributions to the Rubin Commissioning Team from DESC members.
8. Evolving the CTF to become the interface between the DESC and Rubin commissioning efforts once DESC members are fully integrated in the Commissioning Team.

3.3 Analysis Working Groups

3.3.1 Clusters of Galaxies

Summary: Measurements of the mass function of galaxy clusters (the number density as a function of mass and redshift) are sensitive to both the expansion history and growth of structure in the Universe. These measurements can provide powerful constraints on dark energy and fundamental physics, and are critical in distinguishing between dark energy and modified gravity models of cosmic acceleration. Measurements of the clustering of clusters, the baryonic mass fraction in clusters, and the tomographic lensing signatures through clusters provide additional ways to constrain cosmology. As with all cosmological probes, the key to extracting robust cosmological constraints from clusters is the control of systematic uncertainties, particularly those associated with relating the observed properties of clusters to the underlying matter distribution. This requires a coordinated, multi-probe (multiple optical signatures and other wavelength data) approach and the application of rigorous statistical methods, informed by simulations.

The four main steps in extracting robust cosmological constraints from the observed number density of galaxy clusters are: 1) constructing the observed catalogs of clusters; 2) determining the statistical relationships between observed cluster properties and halo mass; 3) predicting the halo distribution (e.g., mass function, clustering, and individual mass distributions) as a function of cosmological parameters; and 4) extracting the cosmological information of interest using a self-consistent likelihood analysis. LSST data will be critical for steps 1 and 2, while DESC analyses will define the state-of-the-art for steps 1–4.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Cluster detection
 - (a) Develop one or more high-quality photometric cluster finders.
 - (b) Validate cluster finder(s) on DESC simulations and cross-compare cluster finder performance.
2. Characterization of the survey observable–mass relation (in close collaboration with MCP)

- (a) Develop parametric models that adequately describe the relation between the survey mass observables and cluster mass, including the impact of cluster miscentering, halo triaxiality, profile model, and projection effects. Characterize and parameterize how these effects impact the recovered weak lensing profiles and resulting weak lensing mass estimates of galaxy clusters.
 - (b) Develop tools for analyzing the weak lensing profiles of galaxy clusters for the purposes of determining the mean relation between cluster observable and cluster mass.
 - (c) Validate tools to analyze weak lensing profiles on DESC simulations.
 - (d) Develop tools for integrating various optical observables for cluster mass measurements, including magnification, convergence, and cluster 2-point correlations.
 - (e) Validate tools for cluster optical observables on DESC simulations and characterize corresponding systematic errors.
 - (f) Develop tools to combine optical cluster measurements for cosmological constraints. Characterize and validate on DESC simulations.
 - (g) Utilize simulated and multi-wavelength cluster data sets to provide critical priors on the shape of the parametric model, and the scatter in cluster observable at fixed mass.
3. Accurate cosmological predictions
- (a) Develop accurate models/emulators of the halo mass function, and the halo–mass and halo–halo correlation functions in the Core Cosmology Library (CCL).
 - (b) Characterize the robustness of these predictions to neutrino and baryonic effects.
4. Likelihood framework (in close collaboration with MCP)
- (a) Combine the above components into a single cosmological-inference pipeline, and stress-test the pipeline by application to simulated and existing cluster data sets, as well as early commissioning data.

3.3.2 Dark Matter

Summary: The Dark Matter (DKM) working group aims to utilize LSST data to study the fundamental nature of dark matter, including its particle mass, self-interaction strength, non-gravitational couplings to the Standard Model, and compact object abundances. Studies of the fundamental nature of dark matter with LSST are highly synergistic, both scientifically and

3: Working Groups - Dark Matter

technically, with studies of dark energy. The DKM WG serves as a central location for coordinating analyses of dark matter physics within LSST DESC. This working group helps initiate cross-working group analyses, hosts discussions of dark matter probes with LSST, and helps coordinate the theoretical interpretation of multiple dark matter probes. The DKM WG also helps coordinate dark-matter-related interactions between DESC and the larger LSST science community.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Measuring the minimum halo mass to test light thermal relics and other dark matter models that suppress halo formation.
 - (a) Developing methods to enhance the identification and characterization of ultra-faint galaxies and stellar streams around the Milky Way, such as improved methods of star-galaxy separation, using multi-band stellar photometry and proper motions to identify candidate member stars, and removing imaging artifacts.
 - (b) Collaborating in the search for strong lens systems and developing methods to characterize dark matter substructures and line-of-sight halos using, for example, gravitational imaging, flux ratio anomalies, and time-delay anomalies (with the Strong Lensing topical team).
 - (c) Promoting theory efforts to advance predictions of the abundance of low-mass dark matter halos and to model the galaxy-halo connection for various dark matter models (with the Modeling and Combined Probes, MCP, working group).
2. Measuring halo profiles and shapes to test if they have been altered by dark matter microphysics.
 - (a) Mitigating systematics that affect measurements of the halo profile for a stacked sample of dwarf galaxy lenses, including photometric redshift estimation for the lens sample, contamination by more-distant and higher-mass galaxies in the lens sample, and characterizing our ability to accurately measure shear at very small angular scales where PSF modeling and deblending may pose a greater challenge.
 - (b) Developing analysis methodology for interpreting cluster weak lensing profiles and locations of member galaxies to characterize features such as the halo radial profile and shape, splashback radius, substructures, and spatial offsets between baryonic and dark matter in merging clusters.
 - (c) Promoting theory efforts to predict halo radial profiles and shapes for various dark matter models (with MCP working group)

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3. Identifying compact objects (e.g., primordial black holes) which may make up some fraction of the dark matter.
 - (a) Developing methods to enhance searches for microlensing by primordial black holes, for example by improving crowded field photometry, deblending, and light curve analysis.
 - (b) Advancing theory efforts to model the abundance of compact objects due to conventional astrophysical processes and primordial black holes (with the MCP working group).
4. Using large-scale structure to explore dark matter and dark sector physics.
 - (a) Studying light relics and other new physics in the dark sector (e.g., potential solutions to the H_0 tension, correlations between dark matter and dark energy). This may involve work to control and measure survey systematics at large scales and baryonic systematics at small scales.
 - (b) Studying from a theoretical perspective the impact of dark matter microphysics on the relationship between tracers and structure (with the MCP working group).
5. Probing anomalous energy losses in stars: dark matter that couples to the standard model may change the thermodynamics of stars, altering their internal structure, evolution, and lifetime.
 - (a) Enhancing stellar population studies, such as measurements of the white dwarf luminosity function, as well as characterization of globular clusters. This may entail developing improved methods of star-galaxy separation, detailed estimates of the survey response function, and developing improved proper motion measurements and photometric calibration.
 - (b) Developing techniques to identify and study core-collapse supernovae (with the Time Domain working group).

3.3.3 External Synergies

Summary:

To maximize the impact of LSST, we will also need follow-up data from other observational resources. Additionally, a variety of projects would benefit from joint analyses that combine data, software and/or simulations from both LSST and other cosmology experiments. The External Synergies working group serves as a clearinghouse and forum to help DESC

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work together across working groups and collaborations for access to the needed data, shepherd cross-working group observing or computational proposals to achieve this, and aid in coordinating the development of joint projects with other collaborations.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Making and maintaining an inventory of DESC needs for external data (e.g., follow-up) or datasets. Where possible, quantifying the gains from such data as a function of sample size / depth / time invested.
2. Making and maintaining an inventory of potential telescope/instrument resources that may be used to meet these needs.
3. Based on these inventories, identifying synergies between different DESC science cases for additional data and developing plans to apply these external resources to maximize DESC science, including both resources that are available through in-kind contributions and those that will require new cross-working group proposals.
4. Working to identify opportunities to increase the cosmological constraining power of LSST by incorporating data from other surveys and the best way to pursue these opportunities.
5. Acting as a conduit to organize the joint analysis of LSST data with other experiments where non-trivial coordination is necessary.

3.3.4 Large-scale Structure

Summary: The Large-scale Structure (LSS) working group is in charge of delivering cosmological constraints from the statistics of galaxy positions (for this reason, this probe is also commonly called *galaxy clustering*). In the standard description, the distribution of galaxies acts as a proxy of the underlying matter fluctuations, and therefore it can be used to reconstruct some of the features left by the cosmic evolution in the distribution of structures through gravitational collapse. The main source of uncertainty in galaxy clustering measurements lies in the details of the relation between the matter density fluctuations and the inhomogeneities in the number density of galaxies. Although on sufficiently large scales there are good reasons to expect that this relation should be adequately described by a linear bias factor connecting both overdensities, a non-linear, stochastic and possibly non-local relation is needed on smaller scales. This relation may also depend on local environmental properties or the merging history of the dark matter halos hosting these galaxies. This group is therefore responsible for making sure that we are able to reliably account for these astrophysical uncertainties in the final cosmological constraints.

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Galaxy clustering measurements are particularly sensitive to any observational systematic that could induce artificial variations in the number density of observed sources. The LSS group is therefore invested in quantifying the key systematics that could cause these variations (e.g., variations in observing conditions, dust, stars, etc.), accurately mapping them on the sky, and developing robust methods to minimize their impact on the key summary statistics used to extract cosmological information (e.g., two-point functions and power spectra).

Because the overdensity of galaxies traces the local matter fluctuations (as opposed to, e.g., the fluctuations projected along the line of sight in the case of weak lensing), LSS is also sensitive to the quality of photometric redshifts, since they limit our ability to recover information from small radial scales. Together with the higher signal-to-noise ratio of the galaxy clustering observables (again compared to, e.g., weak lensing), this has two consequences: on the one hand, cosmological constraints can benefit significantly from using a small sample of galaxies with high-quality photo- z s, and therefore optimal sample selection is a key concern for this group. On the other hand, galaxy clustering constraints are more sensitive to uncertainties in the redshift distribution, and these must therefore be carefully quantified.

Priorities: Historically, accurate measurements of the power spectrum and its uncertainties have been a major research topic of the LSS working group. However, the recently released power spectrum estimation package `NaMaster` is sufficiently optimal and validated that it will serve the need of this group for the foreseeable future. It also calculates the disconnected part of the covariance matrix, and other subdominant contributions of measurement uncertainty will be handled as part of the research priorities of the Modeling and Combined Probes group. Instead, the priorities of the LSS group can be articulated around the main sources of astrophysical and observational systematics described in the previous section:

1. Modeling the galaxy-matter relation.
 - (a) Ensuring that a sufficiently broad range of bias models (e.g., perturbation theory, effective field theory, and halo model approaches) are implemented in the DESC theory pipelines.
 - (b) Quantifying the scales on which existing galaxy bias models can be used reliably without biasing the final cosmological constraints.
2. Evaluating survey geometry, systematics mapping, and estimating 2-point functions.
 - (a) Developing software infrastructure for survey geometry representation.
 - (b) Defining accurate methods to map observing conditions, depth variations and other possible sky systematics. Developing requirements on the precision of these maps.

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- (c) Interfacing with other WGs and TTs on the efforts on Synthetic Source Injections, a promising avenue for developing accurate models of the depth and other sky systematics.
- (d) Robustly estimating two-point statistics (and their uncertainties) in the presence of these systematics.

3. Sample selection.

- (a) Developing science-driven methods to identify the optimal sub-sample of galaxies for large-scale structure analyses.
- (b) Placing requirements on the properties of the clustering sample needed to meet the DESC science objectives.
- (c) Investigating the performance of different approaches (e.g., target-specific populations, blind color-based sampling, photo- z -based sampling) and their sensitivity to observational and photo- z systematics.

4. Photo- z uncertainties.

- (a) Developing methods to marginalize over the relevant uncertainties related to the redshift distribution of the clustering samples. Comparing different approaches (e.g., shifts and widths, full marginalization over $N(z)$ amplitudes, simultaneous likelihood-level $N(z)$ sampling, and auto-calibration). The methods' requirements probably will be distinct from those of other WGs (e.g., Weak Lensing).
- (b) Placing requirements on the accuracy with which the redshift distributions and their uncertainties must be known to avoid biasing the final cosmological constraints (or degrading them below the DESC science goals). These will map onto requirements on spectroscopic coverage or redshift overlap (in the case of clustering redshifts).

Enhancements: Some research topics that could lead to enhancements to the baseline LSST analysis for LSS are as follows.

1. Developing software to estimate higher-order statistics (bispectra, Minkowski functionals, etc.) and to use them for cosmological constraints.
2. Investigating the potential of LSS data from LSST to constrain the level of primordial non-Gaussianity, including through multi-tracer techniques and lensing cross-correlations. Quantify the requirements on the level of systematics contamination needed to make a competitive measurement.

3. Developing infrastructure for likelihood-free inference methods and for Bayesian LSS reconstruction techniques.
4. Developing data compression methods that would enable a robust 3D analysis of LSS with photometric redshifts. Explore the potential of this method to reduce the dimensionality of the LSST data vector.

3.3.5 Modeling and Combined Probes

Summary: The Modeling and Combined Probes (MCP) working group is responsible for delivering constraints on cosmological parameters from the combination of all probes and developing the theoretical interpretation of those results. Combining multiple probes allows us to make more precise measurements of cosmological parameters, break degeneracies between them and with systematic uncertainties, and examine internal inconsistencies that could point toward new physics (or unidentified systematic effects). In general, it is the responsibility of MCP to combine all of the work done by the single-probe working groups to produce the ‘headline’ cosmological constraints from LSST.

To achieve this, we need a consistent way of computing theoretical predictions for cosmological models, including astrophysical effects, across all probes; a way of comparing models with the summary statistics provided by the individual probe working groups (i.e., by computing the likelihood); and a way of modelling the noise and signal covariance between the individual probes to properly take into account the correlations between them. The main software infrastructure provided by MCP is a self-consistent suite of codes that manages each of these steps.

Another responsibility of MCP is to work with other working groups to ensure that non-standard cosmological models can be tested. While most work is carried out under the assumption of a w CDM cosmological model, some assumptions need to be relaxed in order to test alternative models in a consistent manner. MCP is responsible for collecting information about such models, and helping to identify areas where additional infrastructure is needed (e.g., simulations of alternative models), and analysis steps where w CDM-based assumptions have been made and need to be relaxed.

Finally, MCP is the host working group for the DESC analysis blinding effort. To avoid cognitive biases in how we solve complex systematic errors and interpret our results, it is becoming common practice to obfuscate the results of the analysis until such time that the collaboration is confident that the results can be trusted. Once final versions of the data, pipeline, and analysis choices have been locked in, the obfuscation is removed, leaving a final measurement that should not be susceptible to issues like confirmation bias. The machinery and planning

3: Working Groups - Modeling and Combined Probes

required to carry out a blinded analysis are coordinated by MCP.

Priorities: The priorities of the MCP working group center around finding accurate, rigorous, and computationally efficient ways to combine information from multiple probes. In the first instance, this involves improving existing methods to handle the increased volume and precision of LSST data, but we are also interested in finding fundamentally new approaches that can overcome some of the limitations of standard methods such as likelihood-based inference. As part of our role in ensuring that alternative cosmological models can be tested with LSST, we are also interested in finding ways to make observable predictions for such models, and finding new combinations of observables that can test them more stringently.

An itemized list of our main research priorities is as follows:

1. Fast and accurate predictions for cosmological observables including astrophysical systematics.
 - (a) Research into predicting cosmological observables, consistent across all probes, with validated precision and accuracy.
 - (b) Fast methods for nonlinear modeling.
 - (c) Fast methods of calculating real-space correlation functions.
 - (d) Modeling of systematic effects, especially astrophysical (e.g., intrinsic alignments, galaxy bias, and baryonic effects), and ensuring their consistent inclusion in observable predictions.
2. Multi-probe likelihoods and parameter estimation
 - (a) Accurate measures of consistency between different science probes of LSST DESC.
 - (b) Research into how to best combine data, theoretical predictions, and covariances into a likelihood-based inference framework.
 - (c) Accurate forecasting tools to assess model choices.
 - (d) Development and support of code infrastructure (the ‘firecrown’ package) to enable consistent joint likelihood evaluations across multiple probes and including systematic modelling.
3. Modeling multi-probe covariance matrices
 - (a) Analytic models of multi-probe covariance matrices in real and Fourier space.
 - (b) Simulation-based and hybrid estimators of covariance matrices.

3: Working Groups - Observing Strategy

- (c) Absolute targets for covariance matrix accuracy, and effects of uncertainty in covariances.
- (d) Relative accuracy of different ways of estimating covariance matrices.
- (e) Effective lower-dimensional parameterizations of covariance matrices.

4. Effective blinding strategies

- (a) Determining effective blinding strategies for single- and joint-probe analyses.
- (b) Defining criteria for when the data can be unblinded.

Enhancements: Some research topics that could lead to enhancements to the baseline LSST analysis for the MCP working group are as follows:

1. Combining data from external probes

- (a) Theoretical predictions for external probes (such as CMB).
- (b) Requirements for modeling covariances between DESC probes and external probes.
- (c) Ways of integrating external information into DESC cosmological parameter constraints.
- (d) Measures of consistency between LSST DESC and external data sets and criteria for combination.

2. Beyond- w CDM cosmological models

- (a) Identification and prioritization of alternative cosmological models to test with DESC observations.
- (b) Infrastructure to model and simulate observables in alternative cosmologies.
- (c) Identification and implementation of new observables or combinations of observables that can test alternative theories.

3. Improved statistical inference techniques

- (a) Improved Monte Carlo sampling methods, especially for high-dimensional parameter spaces.
- (b) More accurate modeling of the likelihood function when data residuals are not Gaussian.
- (c) Likelihood-free inference techniques.

4. Development of beyond two-point statistics as a cosmological probe (e.g., modeling, likelihood, covariance matrix, forecasting and constraints).

3.3.6 Observing Strategy

Summary: The observing strategy of LSST (including footprint, choice of filter changes, cadence, choice of deep drilling fields, etc.) has a critical impact on almost every science case pursued with LSST, including those of interest to DESC. The goal of the Observing Strategy Working Group is to study the impact of observing strategy on DESC science and to work with the Rubin Project to develop an observing strategy that will maximize the cosmological constraining power of LSST, without detrimentally impacting the other major science themes. We work with the Operations Simulator (**OpSim**) team to produce realistic observing strategy simulations, develop metrics (coded in the **Metric Analysis Framework**) to evaluate these simulations, assess their impact on the dark energy probes, and communicate and coordinate with the Project.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Develop metrics to evaluate observing strategy simulations. These metrics are critical to determine the effectiveness of various strategies for cosmological constraints and consist of two different types of metrics:
 - (a) Heuristic metrics such as sky area and number of visits per field that are expected to correlate with improved cosmological constraints.
 - (b) Emulated cosmological constraints in the form of the DETF Figure of Merit, both for static science probes (i.e., large-scale structure, weak lensing, clusters) and time-domain probes (e.g., supernovae, strong lensing).
2. Perform studies of residual systematics due to observing strategy, for both individual and combined probes analyses, to feed back into the DESC working groups to inform their analyses.
3. Propose changes to observing strategies, evaluate existing simulations and communicate conclusions to the Rubin Project team, via the Survey Cadence Optimization Committee (SCOC), to coordinate improvements.
4. Coordinate with other LSST Science Collaborations (e.g., AGN, TVS, Galaxies) to collaborate on complementary observing strategy needs, and other surveys (e.g., DESI) to optimize LSST observing strategy for synergistic analyses.
5. Continue to evaluate and suggest changes to the observing strategy while the LSST survey is underway.

3.3.7 Photometric Redshifts

Summary: Almost all dark energy probes with LSST rely on knowledge of the redshifts of extragalactic objects (LSST Science Collaboration et al. 2009). Because measuring spectroscopic redshifts will be infeasible for the large samples of targets observed by LSST, redshifts will be estimated from imaging, primarily the observed photometric fluxes in the 6 bands, though ancillary information, including the shapes, sizes, and relative positions of galaxies may also be used.

The Photometric Redshift (PZ) WG is tasked primarily with gleaning individual galaxy redshift information from LSST data but also works closely with the primary probe working groups to improve the estimation of science-specific summary statistics that propagate ensemble redshift information to constraints on the cosmological parameters. DESC will use photometric redshifts (photo- z) in many ways, so the estimates thereof must be sufficiently accurate and precise, and, more importantly, must correctly convey the uncertainty landscape of such estimates.

The systematic uncertainty on the inference of the dark energy equation of state w from weak lensing measurements is roughly five times the uncertainty in the actual mean redshift of photo- z -selected samples; calibration must reach an accuracy of $\sim 0.002(1+z)$ to enable DESC to reach its science goals with the first year of LSST data (The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al. 2018). For many static probes of dark energy, we must also determine the overall redshift distributions of galaxy samples with photometric redshift estimates. The requirements on photo- z training and calibration necessary to achieve the necessary certainty are presented in Newman et al. (2015).

The PZ WG thus aims to address three challenges in parallel: developing and understanding algorithms for *constraining* photo- z , optimally *informing* our photo- z estimation procedures, and using other redshift proxies for *calibrating* photo- z estimates and summary statistics thereof.

To accurately *constrain* photo- z s for LSST samples, a number of technical challenges must be addressed. Any source of observational error that can cause differences between measured galaxy colors and their true colors will degrade photo- z estimates. Typical examples of effects that will require further study include variations in photometric zero-points, miscorrected reddening by intervening dust, or unaccounted-for variations in filter throughputs or atmospheric absorption.

Additionally, photo- z s are subject to unavoidable physical limitations — two galaxies with different SEDs at different redshifts can have indistinguishable fluxes, even under perfect observing conditions. Some sources of systematic error may be a combination of observational and physical, such as imperfect de-blending of galaxies coincidental in the line of sight. The

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uncertainties associated with photo- z estimates must be well characterized and provided to the probe working groups in accessible formats.

While many algorithms exist for constraining photo- z s, they all share a need for prior information, be it in the form of an SED template library, a spectroscopic training sample, or an empirical combination thereof. To effectively *inform* photo- z algorithms, we must mitigate systematic non-representativity in both spectroscopic redshift samples used by data-driven photo- z estimation routines and SED template libraries used by model-based photo- z approaches. That is to say, photo- z prior information must be complete, with mutual coverage, or completeness, between the data and the training or template sets. The PZ WG will develop a framework to characterize the constraining power of photo- z estimators in the presence of such incompleteness, rather than relying on the assumption of complete coverage of the underlying galaxy distribution.

Given the high incompleteness of deep spectroscopic surveys, it is unlikely that our training sets of redshifts will be sufficient to achieve an accurate calibration of actual photo- z biases and uncertainties (or aggregate redshift distributions of LSST samples). Traditional assessment by comparing with spectroscopic samples can give a false measure of photo- z performance due to systematic biases in the populations that fail to yield secure redshifts. Instead, we expect to rely on cross-correlation methods for calibration (Newman et al. 2015; The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al. 2018). Key challenges for *calibration* are optimizing these methods in the presence of confounding effects such as dust extinction, lensing magnification and bias evolution and demonstrating that they will achieve the high accuracy needed for LSST.

In addition to developing methods of dealing with these challenges, the PZ WG must develop the infrastructure needed for generating redshift estimates required by DESC (whether point estimates, probability distribution functions, or samples from a PDF), optimizing those algorithms, and calibrating the results.

Priorities:

1. Characterization of redshifts of individual objects:
 - (a) Enabling characterization of individual object redshifts from incomplete training data.
 - (b) Development and testing of scalable forward modeling capabilities for galaxy photometry that allows for an accurate treatment of modeling error as well as systematics like selection functions and systematic uncertainties in the modeling of photometric errors.
 - (c) Development of redshift estimation and calibration methodology for individual galaxy redshift estimation that utilizes partially smaller calibration fields based on

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multi-band photometry or Deep Drilling Fields.

- (d) Development and implementation of statistical tests to validate the probability calibration of individual galaxy redshift distributions as a function of color.
 - (e) Unbiased and optimal (or nearly optimal) compression and scalable evaluation of the redshift likelihood function.
2. Calibration of the redshift distribution $N(z)$ for a set of objects:
- (a) Calibration of $N(z)$ by cross-correlation with spectroscopic samples.
 - (b) Calibration of $N(z)$ by cross-correlation with photometric samples, e.g. by utilizing galaxy subsamples with highly accurate photometric redshifts such as Luminous Red Galaxies.
 - (c) Calibration of $N(z)$ using other external or internal data such as CMB lensing or internal shear cross-correlation.
 - (d) Developing and testing methodology to estimate $N(z)$ based on individual galaxy redshift estimates.
 - (e) Development of methodology to jointly constrain $N(z)$ using all available complementary data sources, i.e. spatial cross-correlations and photometry.
 - (f) Statistically robust marginalization over residual uncertainty.
3. Development of guidance for the definition of tomographic clustering or weak lensing samples from primary observables that are optimal for individual analysis, in collaboration with the LSS and WL working groups.

Enhancements:

1. Joint modeling of systematics such as galaxy bias, intrinsic alignments, and photometric redshift uncertainties based on principled physical modeling.
2. Development of inferences schemes that allow for the inclusion of cross-covariances between the data vectors that constrain sample redshift distributions and cosmological probes such as 3x2pt.
3. Joint 2D probability distributions of redshift and other quantities, the so-called 2D photometric PDF $p(z, \alpha)$, where α is some ancillary property such as stellar mass or star-formation rate.

3.3.8 Time Domain

Summary:

The Time Domain working group (TD) is focused on the use of LSST data to probe cosmological parameters using transient and variable astrophysical phenomena. The cosmological probes developed by TD include supernovae, primarily those of type Ia (SNe Ia), and Strong Lens (SL) systems.

SNe Ia are standardizable candles first used to discover the accelerating expansion of the Universe. They are now a mature cosmological probe sensitive to the expansion history, and therefore can strongly constrain the difference between the amount of dark energy Ω_{DE} and the amount of dark matter Ω_{M} . The calibrated apparent magnitude of each SN Ia is used to estimate a luminosity distance $d_L(z)$, while the redshift z of each source (either spectroscopic or photometric) can be directly converted into a recession velocity. The combination of these two quantities traces the expansion history of the Universe. LSST will identify hundreds of thousands of SNe over a large redshift range, two orders of magnitude more objects than all extant SN surveys combined. This large homogeneous sample of objects will provide strong constraints on the equation of state of dark energy w , any potential evolution of it over cosmic time, $w(a)$, as well as a high-precision test of the homogeneity and isotropy of the dark energy.

SL systems discovered in LSST will include lensed quasar and SN systems that result in time delays and require multi-year light curves, and multiple source plane lenses (or ‘compound lenses’). Cosmographic inference from these systems requires detailed mass modelling and spectroscopic follow up. SL cosmological probes will rely on a smaller number of carefully selected and very well characterized systems, and will be the only technique that uses a dimensional quantity (time delays are measured in units of time), and so will provide an important cross check and complementary information to other LSST probes.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Optimizing the measurement of the SN flux:
 - (a) Working with the Observing Strategy Working Group to optimize the LSST observing strategy to improve SN Ia distance estimates and ensure best leverage in cosmological parameter space.
 - (b) Validating LSST difference image analysis with simulated images and external datasets.
 - (c) Testing alternate methods of background subtraction (e.g., scene modeling).
 - (d) Work alongside the Point Spread Function Working Group to estimate the impact of PSF errors on SN analysis and improve PSF modeling.

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- (e) Measuring biases in photometry as a function of host galaxy brightness, S/N, galactocentric distance.
2. Identifying SNe within the LSST alert stream:
 - (a) Testing different methods to identify the sub-classes of SNe in the LSST alert stream, working with broker teams to incorporate a DESC SN classifier.
 - (b) Determining the selection function imposed by the full measurement chain and its effect on cosmological measurement (even if brokers are independent of DESC).
 - (c) Understanding the impact of contamination from other classes of SNe on the cosmological analysis.
 3. Extracting calibrated SN light curves and necessary metadata from LSST images:
 - (a) Identifying which features of the SN host-environment we should extract from the images for downstream analysis.
 - (b) Ensuring with the Photometric Calibration Working Group that the time-dependent flux calibration and model of the throughput of the system is monitored for SN analysis.
 - (c) Ensuring with the Photo- z Working Group that photometric redshifts for SN hosts are available.
 - (d) Working alongside the LSST Galaxies Science Collaboration to collect metadata from each host such as stellar mass, rest-frame colors, or star-formation rate.
 4. Obtaining spectroscopic information for a subset of SNe:
 - (a) Devising and testing a recommendation system that prioritizes SN candidates identified in the alert stream for ‘live’ spectroscopy.
 - (b) Devising and testing a recommendation system that prioritizes SN host galaxies for spectroscopic redshift measurement,
 - (c) Identifying and applying to use community resources for spectroscopic follow-up, coordinating with the External Synergies Working Group wherever possible,
 - (d) Examining the utility of an active learning system that improves classifier performance with every spectrum obtained.
 - (e) Constructing and validating a full pipeline for a spectroscopic sample analysis based on DDFs after year 1.
 5. Understanding the correlations between SNe and their host environment:

- (a) Determining how host-galaxy information can be used to improve classification.
 - (b) Determining how to plausibly embed simulated SNe in host galaxies in a manner that preserves correlations.
 - (c) Identifying the underlying physics of the SN-host mass correlation and determining how best to model the effect for our cosmological analysis.
6. Developing improved models to standardize SNe for distance measurement:
- (a) Improving light-curve fitting methods to better model the diversity of SNe Ia.
 - (b) Extending light-curve fitters into the rest-frame ultraviolet for use at higher redshift.
 - (c) Extending light-curve fitters to accept photometric redshift distributions.
 - (d) Extending light-curve fitters to incorporate host-galaxy information to better model distances.
 - (e) Determining how many SNe need infrared observations for tighter cosmological constraints from a combined optical + NIR sample.
7. Simulating the measurement chain to understand biases introduced in cosmological inference:
- (a) Propagating knowledge of time-dependent calibrations into simulations of SNe.
 - (b) Refining SN rate models, and incorporating realistic photometric contamination.
 - (c) Incorporating SN-host galaxy correlations into simulations at the pixel level.
 - (d) Generalizing the bias model to account for more-complex effects.
 - (e) Determining what subsample reduces/eliminates bias corrections.
8. Finding, monitoring and characterizing time-delay strong lens systems:
- (a) Developing a pipeline for monitoring SL systems.
 - (b) Performing time-delay inference from SL systems observations.
 - (c) Following-up SL systems, including lensed SNe and quasars, with other observations.
9. Detecting and modeling compound lens sources from LSST static images:
- (a) Developing candidate extraction algorithms.
 - (b) Modeling the weak lensing effects from galaxy number density estimations.
 - (c) Implementing the estimation of line-of-sight mass profiles.
 - (d) Developing pipelines for discovery of faint compound systems in coadded images.

10. Inferring cosmological parameters from the modeled compound and time-delay systems:
 - (a) Modeling self-calibrated lensing systematics including lens model assumptions (lens galaxy mass distribution), environmental effects (including halo vs. stellar mass relation), line-of-sight structure, and compound lensing in the double source plane.
 - (b) Evaluating calibrated lensing systematics, including time-delay measurement systematics, selection bias, photometry issues including blending, photo- z and \mathcal{M} errors in environmental analysis.

Enhancements: Some research topics that could lead to enhancements to the baseline LSST analysis for this working group are as follows.

1. Detection of SNe Ia within dwarf galaxies, to define a subset that may lead to lower biases in the cosmological analysis.
2. Using SNe to test assumptions of isotropy and homogeneity
3. Using Hubble diagram residuals to measure peculiar velocities to infer the cosmological growth rate.
4. Understanding the impact of WL on SN Ia distance determination.
5. Using strongly lensed SNe for cosmological inference.
6. Investigating the cosmological utility of gravitational wave sources as standard sirens, or other explosive transients as standardizable candles.
7. Enabling a community-driven model of inferring time delays, to compute more accurate diagnostics and SL figures-of-merit.
8. Enabling community mass modeling of compound lenses.

3.3.9 Weak Lensing

Summary: Weak lensing (WL) as a cosmological probe is based on the fact that light emitted from background galaxies is continuously deflected as it travels through the gravitational potential of the matter density field. The statistical properties of the distorted galaxy images, quantified by the shear field, reflect the statistical properties of the matter density field, which constrain the growth of structure and the geometry of the universe.

The primary observables that WL uses from the LSST data set are the shapes of galaxies, from which we infer the shear signal. A second necessary component is the redshift distribution of the galaxies inferred from multi-band photometry. Therefore, measuring and validating shear measurements and validating sample photometric redshift distributions in collaboration with the PZ WG are essential tasks of the WL WG.

In addition to acquiring the basic observables, the WL WG has active R&D projects on techniques to constrain cosmological parameters via a number of summary statistics of the shear field. In a likelihood analysis these summary statistics are forward modeled as a function of cosmological and systematics parameters and compared to the observations, taking into account the correlation and statistical uncertainties of the data (quantified by the covariance matrix).

The most commonly used summary statistics in WL include cosmic shear (correlating galaxy shapes with galaxy shapes) and galaxy-galaxy lensing (correlating galaxy positions and galaxy shapes). Combining these two summary statistics with galaxy clustering (correlating galaxy positions with galaxy positions) forms a set of three two-point functions that is often referred to as the “ 3×2 pt analysis”. These 3×2 pt analyses combine the power of WL and the large-scale structure (LSS) analyses, which increases not only the cosmological constraining power, but also the robustness to systematics. Beyond two-point statistics, there is also a large range of higher-order statistics that capture the non-Gaussian information in the matter field.

Systematics control and mitigation are at the heart of the work of the WL WG and the level to which WL from LSST data can constrain cosmology will be determined by our ability to 1) control uncertainties in measuring the shear and redshifts from LSST galaxies and 2) model astrophysical systematics, such as baryonic feedback processes, the intrinsic alignment of galaxies (which can masquerade as shear correlations), the non-linear evolution of the matter density field, and the galaxy-halo connection. Simulations, analytical calculations, and improved statistical methods play a critical role in this endeavor.

Priorities: The priorities of this working group can be broadly characterized as follows.

1. Images to shear catalog:

- (a) Develop and integrate shear algorithms in coordination with the Rubin DM software team. We are working on several WL shear estimation pipelines (e.g., Metacalibration, Bayesian Fourier Domain) to generate shear catalogs.
- (b) Develop a testing and calibration suite for shear catalogs (combined with photo- z): The testing suite uses a dedicated software framework that encodes all relevant tests ranging from catalog-level to summary statistics. The calibration framework uses image simulations to correct for or characterize inherent biases in the methods.

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- (c) Quantify residual uncertainties in shear calibration due to instrumental and observing systematics (in close collaboration with BL, PSF and SA WGs).
- 2. Shear, photo- z , LSS catalog to summary statistics (in close collaboration with PZ and LSS):
 - (a) Extract reliable second-order summary statistics such as the 3×2 pt analysis.
 - (b) Work with PZ and LSS to quantify, at the summary statistics level, residual uncertainties in shear calibration and photo- z for relevant galaxy samples.
 - (c) Develop a blinding strategy at the catalog level and downstream (in close collaboration with MCP).
- 3. Summary statistics to cosmology (in close collaboration with MCP):
 - (a) Develop WL-only and 3×2 pt covariance matrices.
 - (b) Develop WL-only and 3×2 pt forward modeling machinery.
 - (c) Quantify residual modeling uncertainties for astrophysics systematics (e.g., baryons, intrinsic alignment) and theory approximations.
 - (d) Develop a reliable sampling and inference method, as well as metrics to quantify internal and external (non-LSST data sets) consistency.
 - (e) Optimize observing strategy for cosmology from WL and 3×2 pt analyses (in close collaboration with OS).

Enhancements: Some research topics that could lead to enhancements to the baseline LSST analysis for this working group are as follows.

- 1. Develop a pipeline for non-Gaussian statistics: Higher-order statistics (bi-spectra, tri-spectra, log-transformations of the shear field, etc.) or direct map-reconstruction based inference contain valuable cosmological information that will add to the standard two-point function analysis.
- 2. Joint analyses with synergistic data sets that specifically target WL systematics: Joint analysis of WL+X, or 3×2 pt+X will increase cosmological information, but the cost-benefit calculation varies strongly as a function of X. Identifying the most-important synergistic data sets to offset WL systematics (baryons, intrinsic alignment, shear+photo- z calibration) is critical to efficiently allocate the limited resources in DESC for building corresponding analysis pipelines.

4 Appendices

4.1 Acronym Definitions

BAO	Baryon Acoustic Oscillations
BL	Blending, a DESC technical working group
CO	Computing, a DESC computing working group
COM	Commissioning, the DESC data & validation working group
CL	Galaxy Clusters, a DESC analysis working group
CMB	Cosmic Microwave Background
ComCam	LSST Commissioning Camera
CSS	Cosmological and Survey Simulations, a DESC computing working group
DC	Data Challenge
DDF	Deep-Drilling Field (deeper regions of observation within the LSST survey footprint)
DES	Dark Energy Survey
DESC	Dark Energy Science Collaboration
DESI	Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument
DKM	Dark Matter, a DESC analysis working group
DM	Rubin Observatory / LSST Data Management
DM Stack	The suite of LSST Project data processing software
DOE	U.S. Department of Energy
DP	Data Product
DR	Data Release (typically referring to LSST's data releases once the survey starts)
EDI	Equity, Diversion, and Inclusion
ES	External Synergies, a DESC analysis working group
FY	U.S. federal financial year (e.g., FY20 started in October 2019)
HSC-SSP	Hyper Suprime-Cam Subaru Strategic Program
KiDS	
Kilo-Degree Survey LSS	Large Scale Structure, a DESC analysis working group
LSST	Legacy Survey of Space and Time
MCP	Modeling and Combined Probes, a DESC analysis working group
NERSC	National Energy Research Scientific Computing Center
OS	Observing Strategy, a DESC analysis working group
PC	Photometric Corrections, a DESC technical working group

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PSF	Point-Spread Function, a DESC technical working groups
PZ	Photometric Redshifts, a DESC analysis working group
SA or SAWG	Sensor Anomalies, a DESC technical working group
SED	Spectral Energy Distribution
SL	Strong Lensing
SN	Supernovae
SRD	Science Requirements Document (either for the LSST project or the DESC, depending on context)
SRV	Science Release and Validation, a DESC computing working group
SV	Science Verification
TD	Time Domain, a DESC analysis working group
WFD	Wide-Fast-Deep (a term used to describe the basic observational strategy of the main LSST survey)
WG	Working Group
WL	Weak Gravitational Lensing, a DESC analysis working group

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